

Sustainable Web Design

Policy Recommendations for Mitigating the Environmental Impact of United Nations' Websites

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Colophon

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Abbreviations

ACUNS	Academic Council on the United Nations System
CEB	Chief Executives Board for Coordination
COP	Conference of the Parties
CSRD	Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
DTN	Digital Technology Network
ECBI	European Capacity Building Initiative
GHG	Greenhouse Gas
HTML	HyperText Markup Language
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
JIU	Joint Inspection Unit
KB	Kilobyte
MB	Megabyte
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
SWD	Sustainable Web Design
UN	United Nations
UN/CEFACT	United Nations Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business
UNCTAD	United Nations Conference on Trade and Development
UNDP	United Nations Development Programme
UNEP	United Nations Environment Programme
UNESCO	United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
UNFPA	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNHCR	United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees
UNICEF	United Nations Children's Fund
UN/ICTAC	ICT Advisory Committee
UNIDO	United Nations Industrial Development Organisation

UNITAR	United Nations Institute for Training and Research
UNODC	United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime
UNOPS	United Nations Office for Project Services
UN/OICT	United Nations Office of Information and Communications Technology
UNRWA	United Nations Relief and Works Agency
UN-Women	United Nations Entity for Gender Equality and the Empowerment of Women
UNWTO	United Nations World Tourism Organisation
UPU	Universal Postal Union
W3C	World Wide Web Consortium
WFP	World Food Programme
WHO	World Health Organisation
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation
WMO	World Meteorological Organisation
WSG	Web Sustainability Guidelines
WSIS	World Summit on the Information Society
WGIG	Working Group on Internet Governance

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Executive Summary

In 2024, the internet was accessed by 5.5 billion people—over two-thirds of the global population—making it one of the most pervasive and rapidly evolving forces in modern life [1]. The 2024 Digital Economies Report from the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) recognised this transformation while also highlighting the internet’s growing ecological impact [2]. [2]. At the same time, the UN’s Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (UN/IPCC) has made clear that “the cumulative scientific evidence is unequivocal: climate change is a threat to human well-being and planetary health” [3].

Key Findings

Despite the UN’s commitments and its principle of “leaving no one behind,” there is currently no system-wide policy requiring UN agencies to measure or report the emissions associated with their websites [4]. This oversight has real consequences. Our analysis of selected UN websites under the purview of the Joint Inspection Unit (JIU) reveals a dramatic average growth in size of over 13,000%, with outliers such as the United Nations Industrial Development Organization’s (UNIDO) homepage growing by more than 600,000%, and the UN homepage itself increasing by approximately 109,000%. Our analysis estimates that the UN’s homepage generates 820 tonnes of CO₂e annually, equivalent to 9 million air miles—roughly 361 times around the Earth’s equator (see page 16).

Larger websites take longer to load and require more data, making them costlier and less accessible—especially for the 47% of the world’s poorest 40% who rely on mobile internet via slower 2G or 3G networks [5]. Moreover, 35% of UN agency websites tested, including the primary UN website, are not hosted on verified green hosting powered by renewable energy. This digital bloat not only increases carbon emissions but also creates barriers to inclusion and limits progress on the UN’s 2030 Agenda Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) [6]. As UNCTAD’s Secretary-General has warned, “unregulated digitalisation risks leaving people behind and exacerbating environmental and climate challenges [2].”

There is no shortage of solutions. In 2024, The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)—the main international standards body for the internet—published the first version of the Web Sustainability Guidelines (WSG) (available at <https://w3c.github.io/sustainableweb-wsg/>), outlining evidence-based best practices for “making websites and products more sustainable” [7]. Key principles rely on simple interventions that can significantly reduce the ecological impact of websites while also improving performance and accessibility. Resources like the WSG and other well-established technologies are supported by a growing body of research, including our own, demonstrating that the knowledge and tools to build low-impact digital infrastructure already exist. Yet as our analysis

indicates, there is little evidence of uptake within UN agencies under the purview of the JIU, with nearly all websites scoring an 'F' Website Carbon score (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>). There's little precedent or institutional incentive, and even within the UN's own frameworks—such as the JIU's sustainability reporting—sustainability is not prioritised or explicitly tracked as a key performance indicator for their internet websites. As the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (UN/IPCC) affirms, “we have the tools and know-how required to limit warming [8].” What remains lacking is coherent policy, coordinated enforcement, and system-level accountability.

Recommendations Summarised

This policy brief therefore recommends the urgent adoption of a system-wide sustainable web design (SWD) policy to reduce the environmental impact of UN websites and align with broader sustainability goals. It proposes two levels of action:

System-Wide Actions (UN-Level Policy and Oversight)

1. Adopt a UN-wide Sustainable Web Design (SWD) Policy, using the W3C Web Sustainability Guidelines (WSG) as a planning framework.
2. Set technical benchmarks, including page-weight and emissions targets for all websites.
3. Require green hosting, with all sites hosted on renewable-powered infrastructure and verified disclosures.
4. Integrate sustainability into procurement and project planning, including requirements in contracts and assessments for website projects.
5. Create a shared measurement and reporting framework, with common metrics collected annually and published across the system.
6. Secure endorsement from the United Nations System's Chief Executives Board for Coordination (CEB) with implementation led by designated bodies (e.g. the Office of Information Communications Technology (UN/OICT) or the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP)).
7. Establish a working group on ICT and sustainability to provide expert guidance and coordination.

Entity-Level Actions (Agency Implementation)

1. Appoint Digital Sustainability Focal Points in each agency to lead implementation and reporting.
2. Staff training on digital sustainability practices.
3. Audit and optimise high-traffic websites, targeting quick wins to cut emissions.
4. Update internal policies to include sustainable web design in everyday digital processes.
5. Publicly report progress, using badges, statements, and dashboards to highlight efforts and build trust.

These reforms, supported by CEB endorsement and led by the UN/OICT and the UNEP, would close a critical governance gap. They offer the UN an opportunity to lead by example—aligning technological potential with environmental stewardship. By adopting sustainable web design, the UN can reduce its digital emissions, enhance inclusion, and reinforce its credibility as a sustainability leader.

We urge the Academic Council on the United Nations System (ACUNS) to endorse these recommendations and support a system-wide transition towards a greener, more equitable internet—one that reflects the values of the UN and helps deliver on the ambitions of the Paris Agreement and the 2030 Agenda [6], [9].

Introduction

It has been 20 years since the conclusion of the United Nations World Summit on the Information Society (UN/WSIS), which recognised the transformative potential of the internet [10]. Since then, the internet has evolved from an academic utility, developed at the European Organisation for Nuclear Research (CERN) in the 1990s, into a critical pillar of global infrastructure [11]. It now underpins nearly every domain of human activity, from communication and commerce to governance and public services. Over the past two decades, websites have become integral to the operations of United Nations (UN) system entities serving two purposes: “first, as tools for information dissemination and secondly, as a platform for e-business applications” [12].

The Environmental Impact of ICT

However, as noted in the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development’s (UNCTAD) Digital Economy Report 2024, the “promise of dematerialisation through digitalisation has not yet materialised [2].” As of 2024, the information and communication technology (ICT) sector accounts for an estimated 1.5–3.2% of global greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions [2]. This footprint encompasses data centres, networks, end-user devices, internet-based services, and websites. The internet’s energy demand already surpasses the total supply of renewable energy, and its overall consumption is rising by 9% annually [13]. With over 5.5 billion users and an annual growth rate of 4%, demand for computing power, digital infrastructure, and data throughput is projected to rise sharply, exacerbating resource depletion and environmental harm across the technology supply chain [1].

Although technological advances have improved energy efficiency through hardware developments, data transmission, and web development practices, these gains have largely been offset by the exponential growth in usage and data consumption—a phenomenon known as the Jevons Paradox [14]. The current trajectory threatens to undermine climate targets set out in The Paris Agreement [9]. The latest UN’s Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (UN/IPCC) Synthesis Report affirms that “the cumulative scientific evidence is unequivocal: climate change is a threat to human well-being and planetary health [15].” It warns that to stay within 1.5°C of warming, global GHG emissions must peak by 2025 and fall by 43% by 2030—requiring urgent reductions across all sectors, including ICT [15].

Sustainable Web Design

In response, the Sustainable Web Design (SWD) movement has emerged, leading to the publication of the draft Web Sustainability Guidelines (WSG) by the W3C Sustainable Web Community Group (available at <https://w3c.github.io/sustainableweb-wsg/>). The WSG offers a comprehensive and actionable framework to help organisations measurably reduce the

Social Equity and Development Impacts

environmental impact of their websites.

In an increasingly connected world, the UN's digital presence must reflect its core commitment to equity and inclusion. The UN Charter and SDG principle of "leave no one behind" demand accessible communication [16], [4]. Several UN programmes (health campaigns, educational resources, aid information) rely on web dissemination. If the UN's web estate is not optimised for such conditions, these individuals face significant barriers in accessing content, resulting in disproportionately high mobile data costs and reduced access—an indirect form of digital exclusion. This undermines progress toward SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure) and SDG 10 (Reduced Inequalities), by reinforcing systemic disparities in digital access and SDG 12 (Responsible Consumption and Production) [17], [18], [19]. The implications extend further: SDG 1 (No Poverty), as digital inaccessibility imposes hidden economic burdens; SDG 3 (Good Health and Well-being), by obstructing access to essential health-related information; and SDG 4 (Quality Education), as students and educators in underserved regions are unable to benefit fully from digital learning resources [20], [21], [22].

As UN Secretary-General António Guterres warned in his remarks on UNCTAD's Digital Economy Report 2024, "unregulated digitalisation risks leaving people behind and exacerbating environmental and climate challenges," emphasising that bridging the digital divide requires not only access, but also sustainable and inclusive digital design [2]. A large, technically advanced website may reflect institutional ambition, but if it is inaccessible on slow mobile connections, it fails its mission in the world's most vulnerable regions.

Furthermore, the production side of digital infrastructure has significant implications for climate justice in developing countries. Data centers are often built in emerging markets, mobile devices rely on minerals extracted from low-income regions, and e-waste is disproportionately disposed of in the Global South [23], [24]. While these broader issues extend beyond the scope of this brief, they highlight a critical point: the UN, as an advocate for sustainable development, should actively minimise its associated digital footprint. SWD plays a role here—not only by reducing energy use, but by extending the usability of older or lower-spec end-user devices. By favouring lightweight, efficient websites, SWD slows the pressure to upgrade hardware, reducing the environmental and social costs of accelerated device turnover. In short, sustainable digital practices reinforce the UN's commitment to equity, environmental justice, and inclusive development.

Challenges to Implementation

Beyond the ethical imperative, most web sustainability principles already overlap with established web best practices. For instance, Google's PageRank algorithm now favours faster, lighter, sustainable websites, providing an SEO incentive to minimise "bloat" [25], [26]. Furthermore, not only does this improve user experience but also reduce operational expenditure, such as server costs and energy consumption. Despite these clear benefits, substantive progress remains limited. The absence of enforcement mechanisms, low rates of institutional adoption, and ongoing ambiguity regarding implementation—described by the Green Web Foundation as the "fog of enactment"—continue to impede systemic change, with web sustainability-related tasks, as reported by the JIU are often "swept under the carpet and placed at the bottom of the backlog," reflecting difficulties in gaining organisational buy-in and awareness [27], [28].

Institutionalising Sustainable Digital Governance

Two decades ago, the inaugural meeting of the UN Working Group on Internet Governance (WGIG) made recommendations for inclusive, open, and secure governance of digital systems [29]. Today, the challenge is not merely aspirational but operational: how to institutionalise and enforce standards that translate sustainability commitments into measurable practice. The UN has a proven track record in setting global digital standards. From the United Nations Commission on International Trade Law's (UNCITRAL's) Model Law on Electronic Commerce—which legitimised e-signatures and digital contracts—to the Centre for Trade Facilitation and Electronic Business's (UN/CEFACT's) ebXML framework, which enables cross-border data exchange, the UN has helped shape the backbone of the digital economy [30]. Most recently, the UN Chief Executives Board's Digital Technology Network (DTN) adopted the newly published UN Open Source Principles (available at <https://unite.un.org/news/sixteen-organizations-endorse-un-open-source-principles>). The Government of the French Republic became the first national government to endorse these principles [31].

These successes show the UN's power to embed norms into the digital economy. Today, that leadership and will must extend to mitigating the environmental impact of websites: the same credibility that advanced e-commerce can now drive adoption of sustainable web design across the UN system. Clearing the "fog" requires more than ambition—it demands policy instruments with the precision to navigate complexity, the authority to compel compliance, and the transparency to foster trust. Only by illuminating this path can web sustainability transition from principle to practice.

Problem Statement

Despite the growing environmental impact of digital infrastructure, there is currently no system-wide policy within the UN system to address the environmental impact of UN agency websites. This lack of oversight represents a critical governance gap in the UN's efforts to lead on climate action and sustainable development.

The size and complexity of UN websites have increased dramatically accelerating consumption of natural and abiotic resources contributing to rising GHG emissions, and straining accessibility for the 47% of the world's poorest 40% who rely on mobile internet [5]. These inefficiencies not only limit access to vital information but also stall progress on the SDGs.

Without web sustainability standards, the UN risks contributing to indirect greenwashing, eroding trust and fuelling climate scepticism. The JIU has flagged the broader issue: environmental sustainability across internal UN systems remains "fragmented", with missed opportunities for impact and efficiency [12].

Without coordinated action, the UN risks falling short of its mandate to model best practice. A system-wide approach to SWD is urgently needed to close this gap, align digital operations with climate commitments, and uphold the UN's credibility as a leader in sustainability—consistent with its obligations under The Paris Agreement and its role in delivering on the 2030 Agenda [6], [9].

Evidence

Methodology

To support our recommendations, we examine both technical and contextual evidence concerning digital sustainability within the UN system. The evidence underpinning this report is based on a multi-method research design, incorporating primary data collection, case analysis, and a comprehensive desk review. Primary research involves a longitudinal study of websites from across the UN system under the purview of the JIU using a novel methodology we have developed using data from the Wayback Machine (available at <https://web.archive.org>) to assess the potential growth of UN websites and their associated ecological impact over time. The desk review draws upon official UN publications, including the UNCTAD's Digital Economy Report 2024 and the JIU's reports on sustainability, as well as a literature review on the environmental footprint of internet websites.

Desk Review

As part of this study, a structured desk review was conducted to assess how UN system entities address the role, governance, and performance of their websites. The review focused on publicly available UN documents, including oversight reports, strategic frameworks, and policy publications. Search terms included combinations of generic terms such as “sustainable web design,” “websites,” “ICT,” “sustainability,” “digital,” “communications”, and “web governance.” These were applied across sources such as the UN Digital Library (available at <https://digitallibrary.un.org>), UN iLibrary (available at <https://www.un-ilibrary.org>), JIU document archive (available at <https://www.unjiu.org/en/documents>), and selected agency websites. The goal was to identify how websites are referenced in relation to governance, strategy, performance indicators, and sustainability.

The review found that within the UN system, the environmental sustainability of its own websites has received limited institutional attention. A key reference—the JIU’s 2020 system-wide review on environmental sustainability—noted that “legislative mandates for addressing environmental sustainability in the internal management functional areas are missing in many organisations [11].” In practice, few UN entities have binding requirements for green practices in areas such as procurement, facilities, or ICT. Although the report recommended the development of a “dedicated policy and related standard operating procedures,” including for ICT, as well as the establishment of training and reporting mechanisms, no system-wide directive on ICT or web sustainability has been issued since, and its recommendations remain largely unimplemented [11].

Moreover, existing JIU reporting on website performance—such as the principal statistical indicators used to measure scale and reach—makes no mention of environmental sustainability (see Figure 1). Even in the figure outlining “key elements in website policy and guidelines” across the UN system, sustainability does not appear (see Figure 2) [11]. Furthermore, within the UNCTAD’s 251-page Digital Economies Report there is no mention of the potential benefits of SWD in mitigating the growing ecological impact of the internet. This silence reinforces the perception that digital sustainability is a peripheral issue, rather than an integral component of responsible ICT governance. The longer these gaps persist, the more fragmented practices become—and the more deeply inefficiencies are embedded across the system.

More broadly, UN sustainability strategies have largely overlooked ICT. The UN’s Strategy for Sustainability Management (2020–2030) and Climate Neutral Strategy emphasise emissions reduction across operations but offer no specific metrics or guidance for digital services [32], [33]. Similarly, UN system action plans, such as those coordinated by the UN

Annex 2. Principal statistical indicators used to measure website performance and perceived scale of importance

Figure 1. Principal Statistical Indicators Used to Measure Website Performance Across the UN System
 Courtesy: Review of Management of Internet Websites in the United Nations System Organisations (JIU) [11].

Environment Management Group (UN/EMG), reference e-waste and ICT energy efficiency but do not address digital content or data usage—specifically their own internet websites. As a result, while progress is being made in decarbonising office spaces and procurement, the digital footprint of UN websites remains an unmonitored and growing blind spot.

An example of these challenges was the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) COP28 (Conference of the Parties) host country website, which faced criticism for its misleading 'low carbon' mode [34], [35]. Marketed as a sustainable web design feature, it simply hid images from view without reducing downloads or device power consumption—failing to enhance efficiency and in some cases increasing energy use, particularly desktop devices [36]. The site received an 'F' rating when analysed using Website Carbon (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>), a tool developed by Wholegrain Digital to estimate the carbon footprint of websites based on factors such as data transfer and energy consumption. Each visit to the site was estimated to emit 1.7g CO₂e (CO₂e stands for carbon dioxide equivalent. It's a standard unit used to measure the impact of all GHGs in terms of the amount of CO₂ that would have the same global warming effect) [34]. Although the site was not developed by the UN itself, it highlights the risks associated with lax governance and the absence of sustainability standards for vendors. Notably, the official 'How to COP' handbooks provided to COP host countries included sustainability guidance for travel, accommodation, catering, and other

Annex 3. Key elements in website policy and guidelines

Figure 2. Key Elements in Website Policy and Guidelines Across UN System Entities

Courtesy: Review of Management of Internet Websites in the United Nations System Organisations (JIU) [11].

operational aspects—yet made no mention of SWD [37], [38], [39]. In the absence of a system-wide web policy, the UN remains exposed to reputational risk, accusations of greenwashing, and inconsistency with its own climate commitments. As the European Capacity Building Initiative (ECBI) has warned, “not doing so [by the UNFCCC] would have major negative consequences for the multilateral climate regime [40].”

Despite these clear connections, the UN system currently lacks an overarching digital sustainability framework. Our desk review found that each agency or office manages its own web presence under its respective communications strategy, with little coordination across the system. While recommendations to unify these efforts by the CEB under a ‘One UN Portal’ known as ‘One Source’, as of the publication of this policy recommendation, there is no unified policy on sustainable website design, nor any requirement to assess or limit energy use [12]. A 2020 JIU review of sustainability further observed that “legislative mandates

for addressing environmental sustainability in... management areas are missing in many organisations of the United Nations system [41]." In plain terms: there is no binding rule requiring UN websites to be energy-efficient or environmentally sustainable.

Governance Gap and Reporting Omissions

Organisations have begun to account for ICT emissions in sustainability strategies. For example, EU organisations under the new Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) will have to report electricity use and carbon from ICT [42]. Yet the UN system has so far overlooked this directive. Without a concerted policy, agencies independently build websites to meet communication goals, with no consistent standards on web sustainability.

This lack of coordination means carbon emissions from ICT, commonly referred to as digital emissions, remain invisible in UN reporting. The UN Net Zero Coalition and similar plans focus on energy use in offices and travel, not on web services [43]. None of the major UN sustainability dashboards include a line item for equivalent carbon emissions. Even in the SDG reporting or Environmental, Social, Governance (ESG) initiatives, ICT emissions are rarely quantified. Meanwhile, some large donors (notably the EU) are beginning to require grantees to report ICT energy use under CSRD/ESRS frameworks. This will indirectly affect many UN agencies (which receive EU funding or work with EU member states), creating a future obligation to disclose digital footprints.

Without preparation now, UN entities may face abrupt compliance costs later. By setting policies now, the UN can anticipate these trends and share data transparently. Lack of preparedness could otherwise force hasty or uneven adjustments later, whereas a proactive strategy allows for piloting and learning.

Longitudinal Analysis of UN Websites

This section presents a longitudinal analysis of the environmental performance of UN host country websites, focusing on homepage data for entities subject to JIUs reporting. This study draws on a methodological framework developed in a forthcoming analysis of the environmental performance of United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) COP host country websites [44]. Our study introduced a longitudinal, archive-based approach for evaluating the sustainability of institutional websites, using archived homepage snapshots to assess changes in page-weight (the total file size of all webpage elements, including HTML, CSS, JavaScript, images, and fonts), estimated carbon emissions, and hosting infrastructure over time. The same framework is applied here, with appropriate adaptation to the scope and structure of UN system entities under the oversight of the JIU.

The decision to reuse and adapt this method is twofold. First, it enables a comparative assessment grounded in continuity and transparency. Second, it reflects a novel method in web sustainability research, where archived data and publicly available website sustainability tools (e.g., The Green Web Foundation Green Web Check (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/green-web-check/>) and Website Carbon (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>)) are leveraged to produce replicable assessments of the evolution of webpages over time.

Following this methodological framework, we used archival data from the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine (available at <http://web.archive.org>) to retrieve two snapshots for each UN website under the purview JIU: (1) the earliest available version archived version (2) the most recent available version, ensuring a consistent before-and-after comparison. Redirects (3xx responses) were excluded, in line with the exclusion criteria detailed in the original study. As no comprehensive public registry of UN agency websites exists, URLs were compiled through a systematic desk review of JIU documentation and triangulated with references in related literature. This highlights the need for the UN to maintain a central, system-wide directory of UN agency websites, this would support institutional transparency, coordination, digital preservation, and more effective oversight.

The analysis addresses three questions: (1) How have page sizes and estimated carbon emissions changed over time? (2) What are the primary contributors to page-weight, and how have they evolved? (3) Are UN websites hosted on infrastructure powered by renewable energy? By tracing these indicators across time, the study offers a structured evaluation of digital resource use and sustainability practices. This evidence base provides actionable insights for improving environmental performance across the UN's web infrastructure and supports alignment with broader institutional sustainability commitments. The full dataset code used for conducting the study, and results are available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15615064>.

Sensitivity Analysis

As discussed in our study of UNFCCC COP websites, this type of longitudinal, archive-based analysis inevitably faces constraints that require a degree of interpretive caution. In particular, "advancements and evolution in web standards, shifting priorities, network speeds, and user experience expectations necessitate a nuanced interpretation of our results and pose challenges for direct comparison, as older sites were optimised for vastly different technological contexts [44]." These shifts complicate direct benchmarking and call for sensitivity to the historical specificity of each snapshot. Additionally, our method uses a simple two-point comparison, which enables a consistent before-and-after assessment but limits the granularity of year-by-year trend analysis.

Despite these limitations, the methodological approach remains valuable as a starting point for system-wide performance tracking. If reporting protocols were implemented, future analyses could move beyond proxy estimation and engage in more robust longitudinal and sensitivity analyses. Establishing such a reporting baseline would dramatically improve the UN system's capacity to monitor, compare, and ultimately reduce the environmental impact of its digital infrastructure.

Results and Analysis

The results reveal significant growth in the size of websites maintained by UN agencies between their earliest archived snapshots (from the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine (available at <https://web.archive.org>)) and 2025. Early homepage sizes were highly efficient, reflecting the technical limits of early web infrastructure and the relatively minor role digital platforms played in institutional transparency, communication, and public engagement. At their respective first snapshots, around 80% of websites earned an 'A+' Website Carbon (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>) rating due to their minimal size and simple content (see Table 1). By 2025, however, average agency homepage sizes had surged to over 12 MB, an 'F' Website Carbon score ($\geq 0.847\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$) (see Table 2). To put this in perspective, based on standard CO_2 sequestration rates, 1,000,000 page views per month over a year could result in a single UN agency homepage emitting more than 10,164 kg of CO_2e —meaning it would take at least 406 trees to offset the emissions from just one UN agency homepage [45].

Among 25 UN agencies with complete results, the average total website size rose from 91.44 KB at their earliest available snapshot to 12,245.33 KB in 2025—an increase of over 13,290%. The median homepage size—calculated across all 25 agencies—rose from 46.45 KB to 6,355.96 KB, a 13,575% increase. We include the median to illustrate central tendency without the influence of extreme outliers such as the United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO) website homepage, whose homepage grew from 8.13 KB in 1996 ($0.002\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$) to 48,811.72 KB in 2025 ($12.583\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$)—a 600,725% increase.

Table 1: CO₂e emissions, page size and green hosting status of UN agency website homepages first snapshot.

Agency	Snapshot Year	Total Size (KB)	CO ₂ e (grams)	Rating	Green Hosting
FOA	1996	54.40	0.014	A+	N/A
IAEA	1998	20.99	0.005	A+	N/A
ICAO	1998	43.07	0.011	A+	N/A
ILO	1996	46.45	0.012	A+	N/A
IMO	1998	27.10	0.007	A+	N/A
ITC	1998	36.98	0.010	A+	N/A
ITU	1997	50.30	0.013	A+	N/A
UN	1997	17.62	0.005	A+	N/A
UN-Habitat	1998	8.98	0.002	A+	N/A
UN-Women	2010	195.33	0.050	A+	N/A
UNAIDS	1997	8.05	0.002	A+	N/A
UNCTAD	1998	20.80	0.005	A+	N/A
UNDP	1997	39.65	0.010	A+	N/A
UNEP	1997	11.31	0.003	A+	N/A
UNESCO	1997	25.63	0.007	A+	N/A
UNFPA	1997				N/A
UNHCR	1996	42.75	0.011	A+	N/A
UNICEF	1997	131.33	0.034	A+	N/A
UNIDO	1996	8.13	0.002	A+	N/A
UNODC	2002	1266.76	0.327	B	N/A
UNOPS	1997	48.89	0.013	A+	N/A
UNRWA	1999	1.50	0.000	A+	N/A
UNWTO	2006	103.50	0.027	A+	N/A
UPU	1998	90.70	0.023	A+	N/A
WFP	1996	28.83	0.007	A+	N/A
WHO	1998	48.89	0.013	A+	N/A
WIPO	1996	11.07	0.003	A+	N/A
WMO	2001	73.70	0.019	A+	N/A

Table 2: CO₂e emissions, page size and green hosting status of UN agency website homepages May 2025.

Agency	Snapshot Year	Total Size (KB)	CO ₂ e (grams)	Rating	Green Hosting
FOA	2025	24120.41	6.218	F	Yes
IAEA	2025	2287.66	0.590	D	Yes
ICAO	2025	8823.20	2.274	F	Yes
ILO	2025	1864.41	0.481	C	Yes
IMO	2025	22749.39	5.864	F	Yes
ITC	2025	5597.39	1.443	F	Yes
ITU	2025	4419.73	1.139	F	No
UN	2025	19339.87	4.985	F	No
UN-Habitat	2025	6874.52	1.772	F	Yes
UN-Women	2025	6355.96	1.638	F	Yes
UNAIDS	2025	15912.15	4.102	F	Yes
UNCTAD	2025	9007.12	2.322	F	Yes
UNDP	2025	10021.46	2.583	F	Yes
UNEP	2025				Yes
UNESCO	2025	3860.29	0.995	F	Yes
UNFPA	2025	7319.50	1.887	F	Yes
UNHCR	2025	3894.75	1.004	F	Yes
UNICEF	2025	5138.28	1.325	F	Yes
UNIDO	2025	48811.72	12.583	F	Yes
UNODC	2025	10982.98	2.831	F	No
UNOPS	2025				Yes
UNRWA	2025	2895.87	0.747	E	Yes
UNWTO	2025	35774.70	9.222	F	Yes
UPU	2025	9739.91	2.511	F	No
WFP	2025	6088.50	1.570	F	Yes
WHO	2025	17306.41	4.461	F	No
WIPO	2025	8054.40	2.076	F	No
WMO	2025	1491.19	0.384	C	Yes

According to Similarweb (a third-party web analytics platform that estimates website traffic), the UN's main website receives approximately 13.7 million visits per month [46]. In 2025, its homepage size reached 19,339.87 KB, resulting in an estimated 4.985 grams of CO₂e per page view. At current traffic levels, this equates to roughly 68.3 tonnes of CO₂e per month, or 819.6 tonnes per year—solely from homepage visits, excluding emissions from additional webpages navigated during each session. To put this into perspective, that's equivalent to the annual emissions of around 443 average UK petrol cars (based on 11,000 km/year at 0.16844 kg CO₂e/km), or the emissions from flying nearly 9 million miles in economy class on long-haul flights—roughly 361 times around the Earth's equator—using the UK Government's official Greenhouse Gas Reporting Conversion Factors (2024 [47]).

By 2025, the average Website Carbon rating was an 'F', with only three agencies (The International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), the International Labour Organization (ILO), and the World Meteorological Organization (WMO)) scoring between a 'C' and 'E' score (see Table 2). This widespread shift to larger, richer websites came at a significant sustainability cost, exposing systemic inefficiencies in modern web development practices. Compound annual growth rates (CAGR) for each agency averaged about 22.9% per year, with a median of 21.8%, confirming consistent, strong expansion in website sizes across the UN system, regardless of when their earliest snapshots were taken.

The dataset does have gaps, caused not by lack of data collection but by technical limits of website analysis tools and methodologies like ours. Attempts to access some archived sites timed out due to long load times, likely linked to the Wayback Machine itself. This reflects broader challenges in measuring web sustainability longitudinally: websites are ephemeral,

819.6 t

Estimated annual CO₂e from the UN homepage alone—equivalent to 443 petrol cars or nearly 9 million air miles.

10,164 kg

Annual emissions from the average UN agency homepage with 1M monthly views—would require over 400 trees to offset.

35%

35% of UN agency websites are not currently hosted on green infrastructure powered by renewable energy.

constantly evolving, and often resistant to automated scraping.

These issues limit the completeness of longitudinal studies and highlight a systemic problem—the absence of standardised institutional reporting on digital environmental performance. If UN agencies adopted routine reporting on website size and emissions, researchers could track growth and sustainability more accurately, reducing reliance on proxy tools and estimations. This calls for greater transparency and accountability in digital environmental impact, especially given the UN's commitment to sustainable development.

The composition of UN agency websites has changed since their earliest snapshots, moving towards richer, more complex digital content (see Figure 3 and Figure 4). Initially, HTML made up 10% to over 50% of page size, but by 2025, this dropped below 5%, showing that simple markup now accounts for only a small fraction of total page-weight.

Figure 3. Snapshot of the United Nations homepage on 2 January 1997 (left) and 30 May 2025 (right), accessed via the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine.

Figure 4. Snapshot of the UNICEF homepage on 22 January 1997 (left) and 29 May 2025 (right), accessed via the Internet Archive's Wayback Machine.

Figure 5: The composition of homepage website assets (HTML, stylesheets, scripts, images, and other files) from each UN agency's earliest available website homepage snapshot. UN Women, UNODC, and UNWTO have been excluded from this figure, as their first available data is from the 2000s and would distort the comparative scale of earlier websites.

Figure 6: The composition of homepage website assets (HTML, stylesheets, scripts, images, and other files) across UN agency homepages as captured in May 2025.

Stylesheets (CSS), which were previously negligible or entirely absent in early UN agency websites, now commonly account for 5% to 30% of total page size. This shift reflects the transition from simple, inline styling to external CSS files, enabling more sophisticated visual design, improved maintainability, and responsive layouts. Similarly, the size of scripts has increased from an estimated 10% to over 60% of total page-weight in agencies such as ITU and WHO. This growth underscores a broader move towards client-side interactivity and dynamic content delivery across the UN's digital presence.

Images have become the dominant factor in website size for nearly all UN agencies by 2025. Early sites had few images, often under 10% of page size (see Figure 5); modern UN websites typically have images constituting 20% to over 80% of total page-weight (see Figure 6). On average, image payloads on UN agency homepages have increased by over 6,740% since the late 1990s to early 2000s. This growth is driven by advances in screen technology with higher pixel densities, increased network throughput enabling faster delivery of large files, and rising user expectations for rich, visually engaging content.

Finally, the analysis reveals progress towards renewable energy hosting among UN websites overseen by the JIU (see Table 2). Of 31 JIU-reporting agencies, 20 (65%) use hosting powered by renewables, confirmed via The Green Foundation's Green Web Check (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/green-web-check/>) and Website Carbon (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>). However, several key organisations—including the UN main website, The World Health Organization (WHO), the International Telecommunication Union (ITU), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), the Universal Postal Union (UPU), and the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO)—do not have verifiable renewable hosting, showing significant room for improvement. Even agencies with renewable hosting should ensure official verification through The Green Web Foundation's process (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/tools/green-web-dataset/get-verified/>) to maintain transparency and credibility. While the trend aligns with the UN's broader sustainability goals, it also underscores the need for urgent action to green the digital infrastructure of these flagship entities.

Policy Options Considered

Our evidence confirms that unchecked web practices carry serious environmental, social, and reputational risks that are all avoidable with clear policy. The UN aims for climate neutrality and the United Nations Inter-Agency Task Force (UN/IATF) calls for integrated sustainable operations. Digital sustainability must move from a technical afterthought to a top-level priority. We evaluated several policy pathways, each with its own strengths and weaknesses:

Developing a Binding SWD Standard

A UN-wide mandate could set efficiency benchmarks (e.g. 'page-weight budget', required performance metrics) for all digital content [48]. This top-down approach drives systemic change by making sustainability compliance mandatory. Its advantage is quick, uniform impact; its drawback is potential resistance (UN agencies vary widely in capacity and autonomy) and the need for new oversight. Implementing this would require training and new audit tools, but it could cut emissions significantly once enforced.

Introducing Procurement Requirements

Embedding green criteria in ICT procurement can leverage market forces. All contracts for websites or cloud services would specify energy and emissions limits (or require renewable hosting). The procurement route is often easier to enforce (through contract terms) and can stimulate greener ICT industries. However, it depends on agencies updating tender documents and may incur short-term cost increases. Long-term savings and reputational gains would offset those costs.

Publishing Voluntary Guidelines

Issuing best-practice guidelines (without enforcement) is low-cost and informative. A UN handbook on SWD or a public 'Designing Sustainable Websites' toolkit could raise awareness and encourage motivated agencies. However, by itself this approach is unlikely to achieve system-wide consistency: agencies already pressed on priorities might treat SWD as optional, and uniform impact would be limited.

Enforcing Reporting and Disclosure

Incorporating digital emissions into the UN's environmental reporting (such as integrating them in existing sustainability scorecards) could create accountability. For example, agencies could report their estimated web energy use as part of annual environmental reports. This aligns with global trends (e.g. the EU's CSRD framework will require ICT disclosures) [42]. The challenge here is measurement: carbon calculators and the underlying models used are still maturing. Nevertheless, even rough disclosures would encourage agencies to address the issue and allow central monitoring of progress.

Centralising System Infrastructure

Some UN organisations have experimented with shared platforms (the defunct 'One UN Portal' was an example) [12]. A central hosting solution and content management system (CMS) could theoretically optimise resource use more efficiently than many disjointed servers. It could mandate high renewable content delivery networks and optimise for carbon. In practice, coordinating such a move would be complex (each agency has its own mandates, tech stack and culture). Still, exploring shared CMS, cloud services and data centres as part of a strategy could yield large gains.

Developing a Communication Strategy

Finally, a policy on how the UN communicates sustainability could be adopted. This would involve transparently reporting efforts to clean up digital emissions, to bolster credibility. It must be carefully worded—vague sustainability claims without action could backfire—but honest, data-backed communication can strengthen trust.

We conclude that no single policy option is sufficient—the solution must be multi-faceted. The strongest approach combines mandatory standards (to ensure baseline compliance) with supportive measures (procurement, reporting, guidance). Therefore, our recommendations propose a hybrid strategy that sets system-level requirements while also building capacity and accountability at the agency level.

Recommendations

To ensure the UN's internet websites minimise their ecological impact and align with the broader sustainability objectives, we propose a package of measures under two categories: system-wide actions (mandated at the UN-wide level through the CEB) and entity-level actions (to be implemented by each agency or office). These recommendations draw on established best practices, are evidence-based, and are designed to be implementable within existing UN governance structures.

System-Wide Actions (UN-Level Policy and Oversight)

1. Use the W3C Web Sustainable Guidelines as a Planning Framework

The UN should adopt the W3C WSG (available at <https://w3c.github.io/sustainableweb-wsg/>) as a reference framework for planning, designing and developing all websites.

While not prescriptive, the guidelines offer a comprehensive checklist of best practices that should be consulted alongside other key performance indicators (KPIs). Their use will help embed sustainability principles consistently across projects, while allowing for contextual adaptation.

2. Set a Page-Weight and Emissions Budget

All UN websites must meet defined technical benchmarks: a 'page-weight budget' equivalent to $\leq 0.341\text{g CO}_2\text{e}$ per page and a minimum Website Carbon rating of 'B' (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>) [47]. For example, if the UN homepage were optimised to meet a website carbon score of 'B' in line with our recommendations, the environmental impact would be dramatically reduced. Given our analysis currently estimates a single homepage visit creates 4.985g of CO_2e , this represents a potential reduction of around 93% per visit. For example, optimising the UN homepage to meet a 'B' rating could cut emissions by around 93% per visit. With 13.7 million monthly visits (Similarweb), that's an estimated 719 tonnes of CO_2e saved annually [46]—equivalent to the emissions of 388 average UK petrol cars, the amount of CO_2 absorbed by 28,760 trees, or from flying nearly 7.9 million miles on long-haul flights—almost 316 times around the Earth's equator [47].

These figures highlight the measurable environmental cost of webpage design and the value of setting clear emissions budgets across the UN system. As media-heavy content may make top Website Carbon ratings 'A' and 'A+' unrealistic, CO_2e disclosures per page should be standardised instead of relying solely on letter grades. This enables transparent reporting without discouraging participation. Emissions should be measured using tools like CO2.js (available at <https://observablehq.com/@greenweb/co2-js-playground>) and monitored via Website Carbon's API or The Green Web Foundation's CO2.js (available at <https://thegreenwebfoundation.org/co2-js>). These requirements should apply to all new UN websites and redesigns, ensuring consistency and measurable progress.

3. Mandate Green Hosting and Renewable Infrastructure

All UN websites and data services should be hosted on platforms powered by renewable energy. Entities must procure web hosting and cloud services that can verify and document their energy sources and emissions, using tools such as The Green Web Foundation's Green Web Check (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/green-web-check/>). Additionally, the UN should require transparent infrastructure reporting: each site should publish its estimated energy use and carbon footprint, using The Green Web Foundation's 'Carbon.txt' to make sustainability data easier to discover (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/tools/carbon-txt/>). To promote trust and credibility, agencies should publicly disclose whether their websites are powered by renewable energy, name their hosting provider, and confirm whether the provider has been independently verified. This could be framed as a new UN data policy element, requiring carbon disclosures on public websites or in annual reports. Transparent reporting will catalyse competition among agencies to improve their digital sustainability and ensure compliance with emerging external requirements, such as the EU's CSRD [42].

4. Integrate SWD into Procurement and Governance

The UN system should embed sustainability criteria in all relevant governance processes. Specifically, procurement rules (e.g., the UN Global Marketplace, vendor request for proposals (RFPs)) should stipulate compliance with the WSG guidelines and metrics-based performance. Any contract for web design, software, or data services should include clauses on energy efficiency and data minimisation. Likewise, large digital projects (such as new websites, portals, or apps) must undergo a Sustainability Impact Assessment during design—like the environmental assessments for buildings—to identify and mitigate “bloat” [25]. Including SWD checkpoints

in project management will normalise the practice of factoring equivalent carbon emissions into budgets and timelines. For example, host nations organising UNFCCC COP conferences, as representatives of the UN, should also adopt sustainable web design practices for their event websites and digital infrastructure, reinforcing the UN's commitment and setting a practical precedent.

5. Establish UN-wide Carbon Metrics and Reporting Framework

A standardised system of measurement is needed to track progress. We recommend developing and adopting a common set of digital sustainability indicators (for example: average page load size, estimate site traffic and estimated CO₂e per session). These indicators should be collected by each entity at least annually. The Office of Information and Communications Technology (UN/OICT), in coordination with UNEP and the CEB's sustainability committees, should publish aggregated data (e.g., on a public dashboard or Secretary-General's report). Over time, this will allow benchmarking and identification of high-impact areas. By aligning with emerging international norms (e.g., GRI standards on ICT emissions), the UN can future proof its reporting and assist agencies when external reporting rules tighten.

6. CEB Endorsement and Governance Structure

A standardised system of measurement is needed to track progress. We recommend developing and adopting a common set of digital sustainability indicators (for example: average page load size, estimate site traffic and estimated CO₂e per session). These indicators should be collected by each entity at least annually. The Office of Information and Communications

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7. Establish a Cross-Functional Governance Body for SWD

Given the technical and governance challenges involved, consideration should also be given to establishing a dedicated working group or governance committee on ICT and sustainability. This group could draw together expertise from across technical, environmental, and policy domains to guide implementation, identify capacity gaps, and ensure recommendations are fit for purpose. It could also act as a liaison body, reporting into existing structures like the UN/EMG, while helping to build institutional knowledge and continuity around digital sustainability governance.

Entity-Level Actions (Agency Implementation)

1. Designate SWD Focal Points

Each UN entity should appoint one or more staff members (in IT, communications, or sustainability offices) to lead SWD efforts. These Focal Points would coordinate the agency's implementation of the UN SWD policy, liaise with UN/OICT and UNEP on system-wide initiatives, and serve as an internal resource for staff queries. They would also be responsible for compiling and submitting the agency's digital emissions data annually. This ensures clear accountability and closes the current "no single owner" gap.

2. Build Organisational Capacity for SWD

Agencies must build internal capacity to apply SWD principles. This includes developing training modules for web developers, designers, and content editors on sustainable design practices. Training could cover using image-editing tools to reduce file sizes through compression, selecting efficient modern formats, and eliminating unnecessary scripts. Checklist-style guidance (such as an SWD style guide or handbook) should be provided. A "web sustainability toolkit" (potentially hosted on UNDP's digital centre or UN/OICT intranet) could compile best practices, patterns, and case studies.

Training should also target managers, project leads, and members of governance or oversight committees, equipping them with a clear understanding of the benchmarks they are expected to meet, the rationale behind the SWD policy, and how to support their implementation institutionally. Raising awareness and skills across both technical and decision-making levels will help embed SWD as routine practice throughout the organisations.

3. Audit and Optimisation of High-Traffic Sites

Each agency should audit its most visited websites or services (for example, flagship programmes or event portals). Using tools like the Website Carbon Calculator (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>) or web performance profilers such as WebPageTest (available at <https://www.webpagetest.org>), agencies can identify their “biggest emitters” and prioritise quick wins. For example, a homepage with multiple background videos might be converted to a static banner, or images resized. These targeted optimisations can substantially cut emissions at minimal cost. Agencies should aim to identify high-impact pages or services and focus optimisation efforts accordingly. Success stories from these audits should be documented and shared across the UN to spread effective innovations.

4. Embed SWD in Agency Policies and Practices

Agencies should update internal guidelines to reflect SWD principles. This includes adding sustainability criteria to IT policies, communications standards, and website maintenance procedures. For instance, social media and email campaigns could be reviewed to remove unnecessarily large media attachments. Procurement teams should apply the CEB-endorsed criteria to agency-level contracts. Additionally, when planning conferences or partnerships, SWD considerations (such as requiring sustainable event websites) should be included. Digital sustainability must become a routine part of every stage of the content and infrastructure lifecycle, from decision-making and contracting to design, deployment, and reporting.

5. Communicate Progress Through Transparent Reporting

Agencies should publicly acknowledge and report on their digital sustainability efforts. This could include adding a clear sustainability statement on key webpages, embedding website badges such as those provided by Website Carbon (available at <https://websitecarbon.com>), or implementing bespoke integrations via their API (available at <https://api.websitecarbon.com>)—as seen on leading sustainable websites featured in directories like Lowwww Directory, (available at <https://lowwww.directory>) and Lowwwwcarbon (available at <https://lowwwwcarbon.com>). Public dashboards or sustainability pages should highlight estimated CO₂e savings from recent optimisations and explicitly state whether the website is hosted on renewable energy infrastructure, including the name of the hosting provider and verification through tools such as The Green Web Foundation’s Green Web Check (available at <https://www.thegreenwebfoundation.org/green-web-check/>).

To further raise awareness, agencies could produce case studies and run public-facing campaigns that share their digital sustainability journey—spotlighting key decisions, lessons learned, and measurable impacts. Such initiatives not only demonstrate leadership but also educate stakeholders, reinforce institutional credibility, and inspire replication across other organisations. Crucially, all sustainability claims must be substantiated with appropriate evidence to mitigate the risk of perceived greenwashing.

Implementation Considerations

Putting these recommendations into practice will require coordinated effort and thoughtful planning and phasing. The UN’s decentralised nature is both a challenge and an asset. On one hand, individual agencies operate autonomously and with diverse digital systems, meaning a rigid, one-size-fits-all mandate could provoke resistance. On the other hand, the JIU has noted, “a prerequisite for an excellent website is effective web

governance with a functioning decision-making mechanism enabling efficient interaction between key stakeholders [12].” UN-wide goals—set, for example, via the CEB—can provide a clear direction while still allowing agencies flexibility in their technical approaches. One department might adopt a shared, energy-efficient content management system, while another could retain a bespoke platform but streamline its design by removing unnecessary features and optimising performance. Both would still adhere to a common ‘page-weight budget’ and reporting standards as recommended [48].

This dual reality is why our recommendations include both top-down actions—such as common standards, leadership structures, and reporting mechanisms—and agency-level steps that can be adapted to each organisation’s context. A hybrid approach enables system-wide coherence while respecting operational diversity. The key is to set shared targets and metrics, not prescribe specific technologies.

Ensuring Strong Institutional Leadership

Strong institutional leadership will be essential. As noted, UNEP and UN/OICT can convene working groups and issue technical guidance. Oversight forums such as the CEB’s UN/EMG or ICT Advisory Committee (UN/ICTAC) could provide governance mechanisms. Progress reviews should be built into existing governance channels—such as sessional committees or the Secretary-General’s internal reporting. Crucially, oversight bodies like JIU should explicitly include SWD within their auditing remit. Its 2020 Review of Mainstreaming Environmental Sustainability Across Organisations of the United Nations system already recommended integrating oversight of internal management functions; website sustainability should now be included within its remit.

In parallel, a skills audit should be conducted to assess whether current governance and oversight personnel are equipped to understand and evaluate SWD-related issues. Where needed, targeted training should be provided to build capacity. A short-term inter-agency working group could also be established to develop an implementation roadmap, assess how SWD can be integrated into existing mechanisms, and advise whether new governance structures are required to ensure coherence, accountability, and long-term impact.

Addressing Capacity and Funding Constraints

Capacity and funding constraints are a valid concern, but many SWD practices require little to no additional expenditure—such as minimising code, optimising images, enabling browser caching, or switching to efficient fonts. These steps often lead to cost savings by reducing bandwidth use and hosting needs. For costlier upgrades, like migrating to new hosting providers or redesigning platforms, a phased approach is advisable. We recommend starting with “low-hanging fruit”: agencies could audit their ten heaviest websites and apply simple fixes—like image compression

or caching—for immediate improvements. These quick wins will deliver tangible results in both energy savings and site performance, helping to build momentum. Larger initiatives, such as centralising infrastructure or rebuilding key sites, can then be scheduled in future budget cycles, informed by early lessons learned.

Building Awareness and Cultural Change

Change management is also vital. Digital content managers, developers and line managers may initially be unaware of SWD, so continuous education and internal communication are necessary. Messaging should emphasise co-benefits: smaller websites load faster, require less maintenance, and cost less to run. Agencies might launch internal challenges or participate in events like 'Digital Clean-Up Day' (available at <https://digitalcleanupday.org>), with recognition for teams achieving significant results. Case studies are a powerful tool: for example, if a UN project achieves a 30% cut in equivalent carbon emissions, sharing that story can inspire others. Over time, SWD can become embedded in organisational culture rather than perceived as an imposed constraint.

Integrating SWD into the UN's Broader Agenda

Finally, SWD should be aligned with the UN's broader climate and development goals. Digital sustainability can be embedded into relevant Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) programming—such as SDG 9 (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure), SDG 7 (Affordable and Clean Energy), and SDG 13 (Climate Action) [17], [49], [50]. Collaboration with the UN's climate finance and sustainability networks—such as the UN/IATF can position SWD as part of an integrated approach to innovation, equity, and resilience. By incorporating digital sustainability into training curricula, sustainability seminars, and innovation labs, the UN can expand awareness and implementation well beyond core ICT teams.

Conclusion

The sustainability of the internet is not just a technical challenge—it is a matter of governance. As global demand for power, infrastructure and bandwidth continues to rise, it accelerates extractive systems and compounds environmental harm across the technology supply chain. With only a narrow window remaining to limit global warming to 1.5°C, the urgency could not be greater [9]. As UN/IPCC Chair Hoesung Lee stated: "Every bit of warming matters. Every year matters. Every choice matters [51]." And with that, every byte matters too.

The UN must lead by example—starting with its own internet websites. In an era where all sectors are expected to decarbonise in line with The Paris Agreement and in alignment to the 2030 Agenda, the UN cannot afford

to embed unchecked environmental impacts into its communications infrastructure [6], [9].

The problem is not a lack of solutions. As the UN/IPCC affirms, “we have the tools and know-how required to limit warming.” What is missing is binding policy, coordinated oversight, governance, and, most importantly, the institutional will to act [8]. The UN must now put these tools into practice across its own digital infrastructure.

For the UN, adopting SWD is more than an ethical responsibility—it is essential to maintaining credibility and leadership. The organisation’s authority on climate action and sustainable development will ring hollow if its digital platforms contradict these principles, fuelling green scepticism. In contrast, a UN system that embraces SWD can deliver wide-ranging benefits: reduced environmental impact, lower operational costs, improve user experience, broaden inclusion, and enhanced legitimacy as a model for sustainability in all spheres. By implementing Overbrowsing’s recommendations, we believe the UN will strengthen its efforts to deliver on the ambitions of the 2030 Agenda and ultimately aligning technological potential with environmental stewardship [6].

The path forward is clear: the UN must adopt a system-wide SWD policy that includes formal alignment with the W3C WSG, defined targets for page-weight and digital emissions, regular monitoring and reporting, and designated roles within each agency. Training and capacity-building should follow, ensuring digital sustainability is embedded across all relevant UN programmes and processes. This is both an ethical and strategic imperative.

We urge ACUNS to endorse these recommendations and task the CEB with issuing a UN-wide directive that sets clear standards and timelines. By implementing these measures and reporting progress, the UN can align its digital governance with its environmental commitments and inclusive development vision.

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Overbrowsing

Overbrowsing is an applied research group focused on advancing sustainable web practices. Established as part of doctoral research at The University of Edinburgh's Institute for Design Informatics, we blend inquiry with action to develop research-driven solutions that reduce the environmental impact of the internet and improve accessibility, aligning technological potential with environmental stewardship.

The term 'browsing' originates from herbivores feeding, and similarly, 'overbrowsing' in nature occurs when consumption exceeds the capacity of environmental resources. This shared origin parallels the unsustainable excesses of the web, aligning with the group's mission.

